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PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 23

Issue 2

Pages: 215-219

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2152

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13240723

Manuscript Accepted: 07-04-2024

Use of Interactive Instruction in Teaching English in Alternative Learning System: A Quasi-Experimental Inquiry

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of interactive instruction on the English language performance of Grade 11 students facing difficulties in the Alternative Learning System (ALS) program. A quantitative, quasi-experimental design exposed a non-randomized sample (n=40) from Monkayo National High School (Philippines) to a researcher-developed, content-validated interactive learning module. Pre- and post-tests assessed student progress. The independent t-test revealed significant improvement in the experimental group's English performance. These findings suggest interactive instruction can effectively cater to diverse needs in ALS English classrooms. Future research could explore maximizing interactive instruction's effectiveness and incorporating differentiated instruction (tailoring learning to individual needs) to further enhance learning outcomes. This study informs the Department of Education, school administrators, and teachers on the potential benefits of integrating interactive and differentiated instruction within ALS English programs.

Keywords: *grade 11 ALS students interactive instruction, quasi-experimental design, Philippines*

Introduction

Teaching English to regular students has become increasingly challenging these days. However, teaching English to individuals who have not experienced formal schooling presents even greater challenges for educators (Tomlinson, 2008). Students enrolled in the Alternative Learning System come from diverse backgrounds and orientations often exhibiting significant delays in literacy. Given the extreme variability in their abilities, it is evident that relying on a single instructional strategy is insufficient. In fact, ALS students have low performance in paper-and-pen test and show lack of participation in assessments and evaluation in the English subject. The manner of implementing the lesson among the ALS students obviously becomes a pressing concern.

The use of Interactive instruction in teaching English is an approach that helps to promote learners engagement and active involvement in the learning process. In fact, in Canada, a study conducted by Campbell (2021) and Tomlinson (2002) emphasized the importance to cater specific needs such as workplace literacy and everyday communication skills of the adult refugees and immigrants. The Canadian community-based ESL programs focus on providing interactive instruction allowing educators to address the unique needs and goals of each learner, thereby facilitating more effective and meaningful discussion in their very diverse classrooms.

Similarly, research in the Philippines by Resplandor (2021) highlights the need for interactive teaching strategies in senior high school classrooms. This study demonstrated the effectiveness of adapting teaching methods to individual student needs in Media and Information Literacy subjects.

In Monkayo National High School's ALS program, low student performance in English is a persistent concern. While teachers understand the challenges of catering to out-of-school youth and learners of various ages, the actual classroom environment presents unique difficulties in addressing diverse needs. This lack of readily available research on the application of interactive instruction within the ALS program prompted this study.

This research aims to investigate whether interactive instructional strategies can improve the learning outcomes of ALS students. No prior studies exploring this specific intervention within the Philippine ALS context were found, making this research a valuable contribution to the field.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the level of effectiveness on the use of interactive instruction in teaching English in Alternative Learning System as an assessment tool in teaching English based on the teaching strategy on Student Achievement of Grade 11 students of Monkayo National High School- Senior High, Monkayo, Davao De Oro for school year 2023 – 2024. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of competency of the students in pretest scores?
2. What is the level of competency of the students in posttest scores?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest mean scores of the experimental group?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative, single-group, quasi-experimental design with pre-test and post-test measurements, as outlined by Creswell (2014). This design is suitable for investigating the impact of an intervention on a single group over time (Cham, 2022). In this case, the intervention is the implementation of interactive instruction for ALS students at Monkayo National High School, and the impact will be measured through their English language performance. Utilizing a control group within the ALS program presented logistical challenges. Randomly assigning students to separate instruction groups, as suggested by Creswell (2014), could disrupt established learning pathways or create inequities in resource allocation (Cham, 2022). Additionally, due to the program's focus on addressing individual needs, forming a homogenous control group that wouldn't benefit from the intervention would be difficult. While the single-group design allows for internal assessment of change within the group (Creswell, 2014), the absence of a control group limits our ability to establish absolute causality (Cham, 2022). External factors, such as changes in student motivation or external assessments, could potentially influence the results.

To address these limitations, the study will employ a thorough pre-test to establish a baseline for student English language performance (Creswell, 2014). Pre-test and post-test scores will be statistically analyzed to assess changes within the group. Additionally, a researcher-developed questionnaire will gather student feedback on their experiences with interactive instruction, providing valuable insights beyond just test scores (Creswell, 2014). This multi-faceted approach will strengthen the study's internal validity despite the limitations of the single-group design.

Participants

The subjects of the study were the 40 Grade 11 ALS students of Monkayo National High School- Senior High for the school year 2023-2024. The section will be subjected to quantitative quasi-experimental research that was having the difficulty in learning English since they find the topic difficult. Since, there was only 1 section of the above-mentioned year level. The 40 Grade 11 ALS students are the respondents whom will be subjected to the experimental study.

Instruments

The Pretest-Posttest was a researcher-made questionnaire to assess the achievement of the students in their Creative-Writing subject. The Pretest-Posttest questionnaire was a 20 item multiple choice questions with four choices for each item administered using paper-and-pen assessment before and after the intervention was given to the treated group. A Table of Specifications (TOS) was also prepared by the researcher so that the items of the test can be distributed to the different skills.

In the study, the researcher also prepared a module that consists of the lessons to be discussed. It has 4 lessons that were included on the different use of interactive instructional strategies that included in the activities and tasks that the students faced during the treatment. The 4 lessons covered the entire one month lessons during the conduct of the study.

Validation of the Research Instrument

The research instrument used in this study such as Teacher-made questionnaire was presented to the researcher's validators and research adviser for comments and suggestions, which were eventually used in this study. After validation, a pilot test of the Teacher-made questionnaire was delivered first to a group that is not part of the study. Assessment was conducted using the Teacher-made questionnaire in order to determine the strengths and weakness of the items. After which, a pretest-posttest was organized, and it includes the presentation of the Table of Specification (TOS) to ensure that the test items were distributed properly to the respondents of the study. The 20 students in the pilot testing were selected and divided into upper and lower groups of score that were analyzed for the validity and reliability of the test questions.

Overall, the items of the sets of questionnaire for administration are all retained having passed the criteria for item analysis. Details of the result are found in Appendixes.

Procedure

The researcher provided a letter of authorization where they all signed granting for approval. First to the Davao de Oro Schools Division Superintendent office for the conduct of this research at Monkayo National High School-Senior High. After, a letter was then promptly given to school principals: to the School Principal IV of Monkayo National High School, and finally to Assistant School Principal II of Monkayo National High. After the approval of the school principal the experimentation began.

The experimental group were given the pretest and the results were recorded for data gathering. Then the experimental group was exposed to the intervention which is the use of interactive instruction in teaching English. After, the experimentation has done, a post test were given to the treated group.

Moreover, the researcher followed the ethical standards in the conduct of the study. The names were not revealed, and any other information was kept confidential. The researcher recorded the data to be submitted to the statistician for the statistical treatment and

was subjected to analyses and interpretation.

Data Analysis

Statistical treatment of data is essential in experimental research. In order to accurately analyze and interpret the various data collected in this study, the following statistical tests were used.

Mean and Class Proficiency. This was used to determine the central tendency between the pretest and posttest mean scores of the experimental group.

T-test. This is used to compare the means between two groups to determine if there is a statistically significant difference between them. In this study, it is used to compare the effectiveness of differentiated instruction in teaching English within the Alternative Learning System.

Results and Discussion

Competency Level of the Pretest Scores of the Experimental Group

Table 1 shows the results of the Mean competency of the pretest scores of the experimental group.

Table 1. Competency level of the Pretest Scores of Experimental Group

<i>Pretest</i>	<i>No. of students</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Class Proficiency</i>	<i>Competency Level</i>
Experimental	40	5.925	28.75%	Did Not Meet Expectation

The above shows the mean competency of the pretest scores of the experimental group. The experimental group has the mean pretest score of 5.925 with a class proficiency of 28.75. The data presented shows that the experimental group did not meet competency level during the pretest.

Competency Level of the Posttest Scores of Experimental Group

Table 2 shows the results of the posttest scores of the experimental group.

Table 2. Competency Level of the Posttest Scores of Experimental Group

<i>Posttest</i>	<i>No. of students</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Class Proficiency</i>	<i>Competency Level</i>
Experimental	40	14.647	76.75%	Very Satisfactory

Table 2 shows the level of performance of the students after the conduct of the study of the experimental group. The posttest score revealed that the mean score of 14.674 of the experimental group with 76.75% class proficiency shows that the experimental group has the Very Satisfactory level. Therefore, the result implies that the use of interactive instruction in teaching English helped the ALS students to improve their performance in the English subject.

Significant difference between the mean scores of the pretest and posttest mean scores of the students in experimental group

Table 3 shows the results of the paired t-test that was conducted to test the significant difference between pre and posttest of experimental group.

Table 3. Comparison of the Achievement of the Students in the Experimental Group

	<i>Mean</i>	<i>t-Value</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Pretest	5.925			
Posttest	14.674	-17.835	.000	Significant

The table shows the comparison of the achievements of the students belong to the experimental group. Paired t-test was used to find if there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest of the experimental group. The mean indicates the result of the pretest scores that get 5.925 and posttest scores get 14.674. As a result, the P-Value is .000 less than 0.05, indicating that the decision is significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and proves that there is a significant difference between the achievements of the students in the experimental group on the use of interactive instruction in teaching English. The data suggests that the intervention or treatment administered have positive effect on their performance.

Competency Level of the Pretest Scores of the Experimental Group. In the pretest score of the experimental group got low mastery level of the subject since their class proficiency was below 50% based on the result. This implies that the teacher needs to use a interactive instructional strategy that can help the students to be involved and at the same time can enjoy the learning-assessment. There are many strategies for effective learning-assessment that can ensure effective achievement outcome.

Campilla, M. E, (2019) stated that, teachers have to prepare of activity sheets/ cards suited to the ability of the learners that will engage the learners and will motivation the learner to participate in the class discussion. As a teacher, we are tasked to keep students engaged and motivated in the learning process (Winarti et al., 2019).

Competency Level of the Posttest Scores of the Experimental Group. The result of the posttest of the experimental group got above

mastery level of the subject since their class proficiency was above 50% that goes to show the difference in the result of their competency levels in the pretest. It implies that the use of interactive instruction in teaching English used by the teacher as tool to improve students engagement and motivation in the classroom has a great effect on the performance of the students in their paper-and-pen assessment of grade 11 ALS students in the experimental group rather than in their pretest score. The use of interactive instruction therefore, shown to be effective in improving student learning outcomes in the classroom. (Garcia & Kuncel, 2017)

Comparison of the Achievement of the Students between Pretest and Posttest scores of the Experimental Group. In the comparison of the achievements of the students in experimental group, it implies that the null hypothesis was rejected and there was a significant difference between the achievements of the students in the experimental group as reflected on their pre and posttest scores. The experimental group exposed to the use of interactive instruction had a significant effect on the treatment. Interactive strategies provide clear concepts that aid in the effectiveness of learning (Bagila, 2019). Moreover, by utilizing interactive instruction and procedures, the students are more interested in what they are learning, remember more of it, and feel happier with their learning (Senthamarai, 2018). In addition, Tlhoale et al. (2014) showed that the use of interactive strategies positively impact Learner's academic performance.

Conclusions

It can be concluded that the use of interactive instruction is a good intervention strategy in teaching English in the Alternative Learning System who are having the difficulty in the English lesson. On the other hand, the different strategies used were helpful in improving their engagement and motivation to participate in the class discussion. Hence, the use of interactive instruction in teaching English is an effective instructional strategy that can enhance student's ability in the ALS setting.

Based on the conclusions derived from the findings of the study, the following recommendations are hereby presented: English Teachers are encouraged to utilize interactive instruction by giving any varied activities that suit to the learning style of the students so that the students will fully engaged and motivated to learn the lesson. Department of Education, school administrator, teachers must incorporate the use of interactive instruction as an effective tool in English class. However, further research in this field is imperative to find more evidence on the positive effect of interactive instruction in classroom.

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